

Mission Operations Working Group (MOWG) Report

EOS Aura Science Team Meeting

September 29, 2010

Presented by Angie Kelly

NASA/Goddard Space Flight Center

Earth Science Mission Operations Project/428

The MOWG, established in 1997, is dedicated to ensuring the health and safety of the Aura satellite (spacecraft bus and instruments) to enable science.

Remembrance of John Barnett

*Dr. John J. Barnett HIRDLS U.K.
Principal Investigator*

**Dr. Barnett was a true friend whose support to the Mission Operations Working Group meetings over the past years was greatly appreciated. He will be missed.
May he rest in peace!**

AGENDA

EOS AURA MISSION OPERATIONS WORKING GROUP MEETING

September 28, 2010

9:00	Greetings/Introduction/Agenda Review	All
9:10	Remembering John Barnett	
9:15	EOS Aura Status	A. Kelly/B. Guit
9:45	HIRDLS	C. Hepplewhite
9:55	MLS	D. Miller
10:15	OMIS	J. Claas
10:35	BREAK (10 minutes)	D. Shepard
10:55	TES	
11:15	FD Report: Inclination Maneuvers, MLS Requests, etc.	D. Tracewell
11:35	Ground System Re-engineering Plans & Schedule	P. Johnson
11:55	EDOS Status	T. Wood
12:15	LUNCH BREAK	
1:30	FOT Topics; Summary/Actions/Next Steps	D. Mantziaras All
2:00– 5:00	Splinter Sessions MLS Synchronized Yaw/MLS Scan (2:00-3:00) EMOS (3:15 – 4:00); EDOS (4:00 – 4:45)	FOT, FD, EDOS, EMOS, and IOTs

Aura MOWG Meeting, Boulder, Sept 28, 2010

Topics

- Aura Activities since October 2009
- Planned Activities
- Spacecraft & Instrument Status Summary

- A-Train Update
 - Landsat 5 Crossings
- Additional Information

EOS Aura Highlights

Since the last MOWG in Leiden:

- 3/03/10: EOS Flight Operations Annual Review #3
- Spring 2010 Inclination Adjust
 - Next: Spring of 2011 (annually)
- 7/15/10: Aura 6-Year Anniversary
 - 6-Year Design Life
 - Consumables through **2018+**

Coming:

- 9/30/10: End of Prime Mission Review
- 2011 Senior Review

2010 Inclination Series

- On March 25, Aura completed the third and final maneuver in the 2010 inclination series
- Maneuver size was chosen to satisfy instrument performance requests, similar to 2009 series
 - The MLS request is to maintain observations over the same location as CloudSat's CPR observations within +/- 90 seconds
 - This request favored smaller burn durations to minimize the mean local time difference between Aura and CloudSat
 - The OMI request is to maintain Aura's beta angle between 31.2 and 18.3 degrees
 - OMI's request favored larger burn durations to reduce Aura's beta angle
 - This request will now be satisfied as a result of the 2010 maneuver series

Long Term Beta Angle Projections

Planned Activities

- MLS Yaw Scan Synchronized Maneuver – October 25
- MLS moon track March 2011
- MLS THz laser on - Summer 2011
- HIRDLS Chopper Restart Operations will continue
- Continuing re-engineering and modernization of the EOS Operations Center (EOC)
 - Plan to operate for ~ 2 months in the Back-up EOC (BEOC) while the EOC modifications are implemented
- **2011 Senior Review—update instrument trend charts**
- A-Train Spring 2011 Inclination Adjust Maneuvers
- Auto operations of the Solid State Recorder-- after EOC modernization is complete

Spacecraft Subsystems

All subsystems configured to primary hardware

- **Command & Data Handling (CDH) – Nominal**
 - *Solid State Recorder (SSR) Anomaly (December 4, 2007)*
- **Communications (COMM) – Nominal**
- **Electrical Power System (EPS) – Nominal**
 - Solar Panel Connector Anomaly (January 12, 2005)
 - *NEW: Solar Array Offset (Reported 11/17/09, Corrected 07/15/10)*
 - *NEW: Array Regulator Electronics 5A Anomaly (March 12, 2010)*
 - *Simultaneously with GN&C Attitude Disturbance*
 - *Lost one half of solar panel (out of 11 operational panels)*
- **Flight Software (FSW) – Nominal**
- **Guidance, Navigation & Control (GN&C) – Nominal**
 - *Earth Sensor Assembly (ESA) Anomaly (May 29, 2009)*
 - *Recovered by re-calibration in Fall 2009*
- **Propulsion (PROP) – Nominal**
 - *Dual Thruster Module (DTM-3) Anomaly (Aug 16, 2005)*
- **Thermal Control System (TCS) – Nominal**

Fuel Usage: Actual & Predicted

(Updated September 2010)

Aura Status Summary

- **Spacecraft Status – GREEN**
 - All subsystems are performing well
- **Instrument Status - GREEN**
 - **HIRDLS:** Continuing chopper recovery activities
 - Chopper stalled March 17, 2008; not producing science
 - **MLS:** Operating Normally
 - Doing periodic Band 13 measurements
 - THz currently in standby mode (laser off Dec 2009 to conserve life)
 - **OMI:** Operating Normally – global coverage every 2 days
 - Field-of-View Row Anomalies have stabilized
 - **TES:** Operating Normally
 - Modified Global Survey Observations to extend ICS lifetime
- **Data Capture/L0 Processing Status – GREEN**
 - SSR Data Capture to 08/30/2010: **99.993322+ %**
- **Ground Systems – GREEN**
 - Continuing implementation of security and technology upgrades
 - Plan to Operate from the Back-up control center for a couple of months
 - EDOS upgrades to support auto ops of solid state recorder is in testing

Aura can continue to operate through 2018 and beyond.

A-Train Update

A-Train Update

- **A-Train Configuration Changes**
 - **PARASOL Orbit Lowering (3.9 km)**
 - **Addition of JAXA's GCOM-W1**
 - **Glory Location**
 - **OCO-2 Location**
- **A-Train Graphic: Original and New**
- **Landsat 5 Crossings through the A-Train**

Earth Observing Constellations

A-Train Graphic

Preview of A-Train Science Graphic

(from Steve Platnick, A-Train Project Scientist)

History

Landsat 5 Crossings with the A-Train

- **Learned in late February that Landsat 5 passes through the A-Train twice every orbit (29-30 times a day)**
 - Crossings began in ~ 2004.
 - Not flagged by Conjunction Assessment System (CAS) due to coding logic error at JSpOC. JSpOC work-around now in place.
- **ACTIONS:**
 - **“Tiger Team”** (led by Dave MacDonnell, CALIPSO mission team lead) is investigating Conjunction Assessment policies and processes to ensure that there are no other problems.
 - **“Red Team”** (led by Angie Kelly) first convened on March 2 to understand near-term risks for the satellites at 705 km and determine course of action to mitigate mid- and long-term risks

Landsat 5 Crosses Through the A-Train

(Click to start the slide show mode)

Situation is similar near the South Pole crossings

Landsat 5 2010-2013 Crossings

- **Landsat 5 crossed the CloudSat / CALIPSO control boxes between January 8 – April 1, 2010**
- **CURRENT STATUS: Landsat 5 is currently in the Glory entry space (space between CALIPSO and Aura)**
- **Landsat 5 will cross through the A-Train orbit (from behind CALIPSO) ONE more time beginning October 25, 2010 when Landsat 5 performs its LAST inclination maneuver**

Landsat 5 Crossings Through the A-Train 2010 – 2013 (Animation)

Control Box/ Landing Pad	Landsat 5 Enters Control Box/Landing Pad	Landsat 5 Exits Control Box/Landing Pad
CALIPSO		April 1, 2010
Glory	June 8, 2010	October 25, 2010 (Landsat 5 Inc Maneuver)
CALIPSO	Mid-May ~ Late Aug 2011	Late September ~ Early November 2011
Aqua	Mid-October ~ Late November 2011	Mid-November ~ Late December 2011
GCOM-W1	Early December 2011 ~ Early January 2012	Late April ~ Early June 2012
OCO-2	Early May ~ Mid-June 2012	

CROSSING TIMELINE

Red Team GOALS

Comply with the
National Space Policy and UN Orbital Debris Guidelines
**“Select safe flight profile and operational configuration;
Limit the probability of accidental collision in orbit ...
to preserve the near-Earth space for future generations”**

Specific Goals

- **Ensure safe entry for Glory**
- **Delay future Landsat 5 crossings with Aqua, CloudSat, and CALIPSO until after the Spring 2011 A-Train inclination maneuver series**
- **Ensure safe entry for GCOM-W1 (November 2011) and OCO-2 (February 2013)**
- **Enable Landsat 5 to continue mission into 2014**

SAFETY is a prime concern – ***“A risk to one is a risk to all!”***

Summary

- **The Landsat-5 and A-Train teams have agreed on a coordination plan and process for mitigating the crossing risks in 2011.**
 - **An Independent Technical Safety Review panel determined that the plan is manageable and SAFE**
- **Red Team will report to the A-Train MOWG on October 4, 2010**
- **NO IMPACT ON Aura**

- **Lesson Learned:**
 - **All the satellites at the 705 km orbit are all members of ONE constellation**
 - **Coordination is critical to ensure safety!**
 - Any orbital changes or orbit maintenance changes must be coordinated and evaluated.**

New Missions

With proper coordination, there is room to accommodate new missions at the 705 km orbit.

**If you know of any U.S. or international mission that is interested in flying at 705 km with the Morning or Afternoon Constellation, please have them contact the A-Train MOM, GSFC Earth Science Mission Operations Project
(*email angelita.c.kelly@nasa.gov*)**

Thank you for your kind attention!

Questions?

Additional Information

Afternoon Constellation Orbital Configuration

- The A-Train satellite teams have agreed to do constellation/formation flying (within seconds to minutes of each other) in accordance with
 - Agreed-upon *control boxes* and
 - *Procedures* for coordinating operations that impact either the configuration or other members of the Constellation.

On-Orbit Assets at 705 km

Earth Science Missions	Number of Instruments
Terra	6
SAC-C*	9
EO-1**	3
Aqua	6
Aura	4
CloudSat	1
CALIPSO	3
PARASOL***	1

Landsat Missions	Number of Instruments
Landsat 5	2
Landsat 7	1

*SAC-C was raised 2 km in 2005 to avoid close approach with Landsat 7 and EO-1

**EO-1 was lowered 16 km below the Morning Constellation in 2005

***PARASOL was lowered 4 km below the Afternoon Constellation in 2009